

THE NEIGHBORHOOD AS A PLACE OF EDUCATION

N.A. Samandarova

Institute for retraining and advanced training of leaders and specialists of preschool educational institutions, intern-researcher.

Abstract: The article examines the development and implementation of effective mechanisms of interaction “preschool educational institution – microdistrict – school – family” in the education of youth in the local community.

Keywords: Preschool educational institution, district, school, family, district institute, district elite, social-emotional education, competence, social awareness.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются вопросы разработки и внедрения эффективных механизмов взаимодействия «дошкольное образовательное учреждение – микрорайон – школа – семья» в воспитании молодежи в местном сообществе.

Ключевые слова: Дошкольное образовательное учреждение, раён, школа, семья, раённый институт, раённая элита, социально-эмоциональное воспитание, компетентность, социальная осведомленность.

Mahallas have been a unique system of self-government in the historical development of Uzbek statehood for thousands of years, based on the basic principles of a just society and the people's opinion, serving to form the traditional customs, history, culture and social system of our people, and having no analogues in the world. It is an institution historically formed as a unique structure of national democratic, historical, traditional, local self-government of our country. Mahalla institutions are considered sacred places that ensure the consolidation of the population and the continuity of national customs and traditions. The word "mahalla" when translated from Arabic means "dwelling place", "camp", "camp", "part of the city". The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. F-60 dated January 28, 2022 “On the New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” defines the priority areas of reforms aimed at strengthening social protection of citizens, providing them with decent living conditions, raising them to a qualitatively new level, and, based on a thorough analysis of the development results of our country, further improving the well-being of our people in the coming years on the basis of the principle “For the sake of human dignity” and forming an active civil society. In this regard, we believe that it is appropriate for neighborhoods to implement the following tasks today:

- Introducing globally recognized social and emotional education (Social and Emotional Learning - SEL) in general secondary educational institutions and neighborhoods and ensuring effective cooperation between neighborhoods and parents in the education of students;
- Teaching students of general secondary educational institutions the competencies of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, building relationships with peers and responsible decision-making, and involving parents and representatives of the general public in this process;
- Increasing the responsibility of parents in raising children in general secondary educational institutions in the direction of national education for students and students of preschool and general secondary educational institutions;
- Initiating the activities of model parenting schools aimed at increasing parents' knowledge of child education;
- Implementing activities aimed at studying, restoring and introducing regional traditions of national education into the modern spiritual and moral education system;
- Creating a system of cooperation "preschool educational institution-neighborhood-school-family" in order to form immunity against crime among neighborhood youth;
- Forming a reading culture in the neighborhoods aimed at developing the worldview of parents regarding the upbringing of their children; Hold an international forum on the topic "Education is the criterion of cultural and spiritual maturity of a person";
- Improving the views of our ancestors on the formation of a complete person and educating young people in the spirit of patriotism based on modern approaches and creating a system for educating neighborhood youth on this basis;
- Developing effective mechanisms for cooperation between "pre-school educational institution-neighborhood-school-family" in educating neighborhood youth.
- Taking measures to prevent unemployment, training the population, especially youth and women, in professions and entrepreneurship, helping them find jobs or start independent activities;
- Organizing youth leisure time in neighborhoods in a meaningful way, including involving them in participating in the "Five Initiatives Olympics" and promoting employment of unemployed youth and school graduates, including implementing the "Youth Employment Program" in the neighborhood.

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